

Quantum $\exp(ipx)$ and Extremization of Fisher's Information

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A quantum free particle is represented by the free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$. This consists of two periodic distributions (in 2 dimensions) such that their modulus is 1. $\sin(px)$ and $\cos(px)$ are a possible solution set. $\sin(px)$ and $\cos(px)$ are, however, linked to a unit radius which rotates in 2 dimensions. Alternatively one may note that $d/dx \cos(px) = -p \sin(px)$ and $d/dx \sin(px) = p \cos(px)$. Thus one may determine the form of a free particle "probability" using the notion of periodicity, 2 dimensions and a constant modulus. No concept of extremization is needed.

It is interesting to note, however, that $d/dx d/dx \cos(px) = -pp \cos(px)$ and $d/dx d/dx \sin(px) = pp \sin(px)$. Each distribution $\sin(px)$, $\cos(px)$ by itself represents a solution of extremization problem, namely the extremization of Fisher's information defined by $I = \int dx P(x) \{d/dx \ln(P)\} \{d/dx \ln(P)\}$ where $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$ and $W(x) = \cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$. Then $I = \int dx dW/dx dW/dx$. Extremizing with respect to the constraint $\int P(x) dx = 1$ yields:

$$d/dx d/dx W = \text{constant } W.$$

$\cos(px)$, $\sin(px)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ are solutions of this extremization equation. In order to have a solution which treats all x points the same in a certain sense, one may choose $\exp(ipx)$. The point is that even for a free particle, the two distributions involved are linked with extremization of Fisher's information (with $\int W(x)W(x) dx = .5 \text{Length}$), although one may obtain $\exp(ipx)$ with no extremization and no knowledge of Fisher's information.

Why should Fisher's information be extremized? Fisher's information is a statistical quantity which appears in the Cramer-Rao bound: $\text{var}(\text{estimator}) \geq 1/I$. One may take the inverse of this equation and consider $\text{variance}(\text{estimator})$ to be linked to a spread or uncertainty in x . If one wishes to minimize this, one may maximize I subject to constraints. Thus there seems to be a purely statistical approach (i.e the extremization of Fisher's information) even for a free particle. This extremization approach, however, is linked directly to the fact that one has two probability distributions in a 2-dimensional object with a constant modulus. This does not have the appearance of any extremization, but is in fact equivalent to one for each distribution function.

In fact, we argue that if $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$ with $\int P(x) dx = 1$, then if $W(x)$ is cyclical/periodic i.e. $d/dx d/dx W = \text{constant } W$, then W may be obtained through the extremization of Fisher's information subject to the constraint $\int P(x) dx = 1$. Thus periodicity and extremization are linked, but in a somewhat unusual manner.

Quantum Free Particle

Consider that a quantum free particle follows $x = p/m t$ (nonrelativistic) on average, but that there is no certain x point, but rather a symmetric x -probability distribution about a peak x value. Given that the particle is moving in space, there should be two distributions, one at time t_1 and the other at time t_2 . These should somehow combine to represent a constant probability at each x , because a particle moving with constant speed spends the same amount of time in each constant dx . Thus one considers two dimensions and two probability distributions $F(x,p)$, $G(x,p)$ such that:

$$F(x,p)F(x,p) + G(x,p)G(x,p) = \text{constant} \quad ((1))$$

((1)), however, is of the form of constant radius rotating about an origin with $F(x,p) = \cos(px)$ and $G(x,p) = \sin(px)$. Thus one may represent a free quantum particle by $\exp(ipx)$. No notion of extremization has been introduced, but one is dealing with probability distributions.

In fact, $\exp(ipx)$ is an eigenfunction of the translation generator multiplied by $(-i)$ i.e.

$$-i \frac{d}{dx} \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx) \quad ((2))$$

It is therefore an eigenfunction of any power of this operator, for example the second power yields:

$$-i \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \exp(ipx) = p^2 \exp(ipx) \quad ((3))$$

It is interesting to note from ((2)) and ((3)) that $\frac{d}{dx}$ changes $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$ into the other with a possible sign change. $\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx}$ changes $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ back into themselves. Thus $\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx}$ is associated with cyclical behaviour so to speak for $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ separately (as well as for $\exp(ipx)$).

Cyclical Behaviour and Extremization

Cyclical behaviour based on a derivative such as $\frac{d}{dx}$ is directly linked to extremization of:

$$\frac{dW}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} \quad \text{subject to the constraint} \quad \int W(x)W(x)dx = \text{constant} \quad ((4))$$

In particular this leads to: $-\frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} + b W = 0 \quad ((5))$ where b is a constant.

Thus there is an equivalence between cyclical behaviour and extremization given a special constraint $\int W(x)W(x) dx$. For a free particle, however, the constraint $\int W(x)W(x) dx = .5L$ because $\cos(px)\cos(px) + \sin(px)\sin(px) = 1$. Thus the idea of extremization is built in without one even being aware.

Consider next the case of a free particle placed in a box with infinite potential walls. One would expect to describe it by:

$$\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx) = 2 \cos(px) \quad ((5))$$

For a particle in a box, one has a probability $W(x)$ with the constraint $\int W(x)W(x) dx = 1$ where $W(x)W(x)$ is the spatial probability. In such a case, one may also link cyclical (periodical) behaviour to the extremization of Fisher's information $\int \frac{dW}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} dx$.

This begs the question: What role does Fisher's information play statistically?

Fisher's Information

Fisher's information is a statistical quantity defined by:

$$I = \int P(x) \left\{ \frac{d}{dx} \ln(P) \right\} \left\{ \frac{d}{dx} \ln(P) \right\} dx \quad ((6)) \quad \text{where} \quad \int P(x) dx = 1 \quad ((7)) \quad \text{and} \quad P(x) \geq 0.$$

Fisher's information appears in the Cramer-Rao bound (1):

$$\text{Variance}(\text{estimator}) \geq 1/I \quad ((8))$$

If one considers the Variance(estimator) to be the spread of x , then $1/I$ Fisher's information represents a bound for this spread. Inverting ((8)) and requiring the smallest variance leads to the extremization of Fisher's information subject to a constraint.

A key idea is then to consider $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$, because it is the form $W(x)$ which leads to periodicity (cyclical behaviour) when extremizing Fisher's information subject to a constraint. It is not $W(x)W(x)$ which is periodic i.e. $d/dx d/dx P(x)$ does not equal constant $\cdot P(x)$. In other words, the notion of a square root probability is crucial.

We note in passing that for light reflecting/refracting in one dimension, the notion of a square root flux/intensity is also crucial because one cannot solve the problem using only the notion of intensity. It leads to only one equation, while rearranging this equation and using differences of squares yields two equations involving the square root fluxes(probabilities). This may be solved for the two unknowns i.e. the reflection and refraction weights in terms of the incident weight. As a result, extremization of Fisher's information subject to $\int P(x) dx = 1$ does not yield periodicity unless one associates $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$.

If one considers the free particle, the probability $P(x) = \text{constant}$ for the particle to be at any x . One must also consider a square root type quantity $\exp(ipx)$ in order to see x probability distributions at work such that they map (modulus of 2 dimensional probability) into a constant.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that periodic/cyclical behaviour is linked to extremization in a certain manner. One may solve a problem using ideas of periodic behaviour, but alternatively solve the same problem using the seemingly different approach of extremization. In particular, we consider the case of a quantum free particle. If one assumes that on average the particle follows $x = p/m t$ (nonrelativistically), but that one actually has a distribution of x rather than a point, then a moving particle should be associated with two distributions (in 2 dimensions) such that this quantity somehow maps to a constant because each x point has the same weight for constant p . A solution is $\cos(px) + i \sin(px)$, but these are both periodic functions i.e. $d/dx dW/dx = \text{constant} W(x)$ where $W(x) = \cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$.

Interestingly, the equation $d/dx dW/dx = \text{constant} W(x)$ is the result of an extremization of $dW/dx dW/dx$ subject to the constraint $\int W(x)W(x) dx = \text{constant}$. Physically, why should one wish to extremize $dW/dx dW/dx$? We argue the reason lies in the Cramer-Rao bound of the

statistical quantity: Fisher's information = $\int dx P(x) \left\{ \frac{d}{dx} \ln(P) \right\} \left\{ \frac{d}{dx} \ln(P) \right\}$ with $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$. The Cramer-Rao bound states that the variance(x) = $1/I$. Inverting means a minimum variance yields a maximum I (Fisher's information) subject to constraints. For a free particle, it seems that the extremization is built in because $\cos(px)\cos(px) + \sin(px)\sin(px) = 1$ and so one may consider a constraint of $\int W(x)W(x) dx = .5L$ where $W(x)$ is either $\sin(px)$ or $\cos(px)$. Thus one may extremize dW/dx subject to $\int WW dx = \text{constant}$ even though it does not appear that one is extremizing at all.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cram%C3%A9r%E2%80%93Rao_bound